

Prediction of indoor climate based on questionnaires

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SUMMARY:

The main goal of our study was the validation of a formerly presented model to calculate the indoor humidity. Indoor humidity is the most important boundary condition for the hygrothermal behaviour of building components. With the presented model, the durability and life-cycle costs of building components can be predicted. The presented work forms the basis for decision making during the design process.

In this study, questionnaires from 38 households were collected regarding indoor moisture production and ventilation behaviour. The questionnaire answers and values from literature were used as inputs in the formerly presented model. Temperature, relative humidity, and air tightness measurements were performed in parallel. The outcome was compared to the calculation results and used to validate and refine the model.

The calculated results fit well to the measured values, if the humidity is in the low to average range. When absolute indoor humidity is very high, the calculation shows variance from the measured values. The calculated maximum is 15 g/m³, which exceeds the measured maximum of 11 g/m³. Theories for the variance have been postulated; however, specific questions for airtight buildings should be included in future questionnaires to determine the reasons for the variance.

The work forms part of the Austrian contribution to IEA Annex 55.

1. Introduction

Different aspects must be considered during the building design process. Cost minimization, durability (over the building's lifespan) and high energy efficiency are three typical performance goals, which can result in different design solutions. The most important aspects for durability are indoor and outdoor climate and the fault tolerance of the construction.

This study focuses on the prediction of indoor climate, which is the first step in the formerly presented probabilistic model to calculate life-cycle costs (Harreither et al. 2012). Values for moisture production in residential buildings were published by Kalamees et al. (2006), Hartmann et al. (2009) and Geving & Holme (2011). Even standardized values can be found (DIN Fachbericht 2010). In this study, daily production rates in homes were calculated based on the above literature values and applied to the data from the questionnaires. Values to quantify the ventilation rates by window opening were taken from Reiß & Erhorn (2009). The ventilation rates by infiltration or a mechanical ventilation system were taken from standards. Monthly mean values were calculated in this study, which will form the basis to calculate the building components lifespans.

2. Investigation

Two housing projects were investigated during winter 2012/2013 in Vienna and summarized in this study.

PSG is a low-rise high-density housing project on the east side of Vienna and is the first project in our study. Questionnaires were distributed to all 91 households in November 2012. By the end of January, we received 39 completed questionnaires, performed 34 Blower-Door tests and measured temperature and relative humidity in 28 houses.

The second project is KW, a multi-storey residential apartment building on the north side of Vienna. Ten flats took part in our study by completing questionnaires and joining the temperature and relative humidity measurements during January 2013.

2.1 Investigated houses in PSG-project

The PSG housing project is described in detail in Zingerle (2013). 91 nearly identical detached houses were built within a social housing project in 2009. All houses have two floors with 52 m² gross floor area (GFA). Each house has dimensions of 4.75 m x 11.00 m. The net floor area is 84 m². Most of the houses have cellars too. Half of the houses are orientated east-west and the other half are orientated north-south.

The houses consist of timber frame walls and a timber frame roof. The ground floor slab and the cellars are composed of reinforced concrete. The exterior wall assembly on the ground floor is gypsum board, OSB, vapour barrier, timber platform framing with thermal insulation and an ETICS on the exterior. The exterior walls on the upper floor have wooden cross-battens and a ventilated curtain-wall facing instead of the ETICS. The timber frame roof is composed of gypsum board, battening, a vapour barrier, wooden beams with thermal insulation, wooden planking, a ventilation layer, wooden planking, and an EPDM foil on the exterior.

None of the houses in PSG have a balanced mechanical ventilation system, but all the houses have fans in the toilet on the ground floor and in the upper floor bathroom. The toilets on the ground floor are windowless but the bathrooms on the upper floor have two windows on opposite walls with dimensions 2 m x 1 m.

We equipped 28 houses in PSG in January 2013 with two data loggers each. One logger was mounted on the ground floor in the middle of the open plan kitchen/dining/living rooms at head height. On the upper floor, the loggers were placed in the bedrooms. When it was not possible to place the data logger in the bedroom, the loggers were placed in another upper floor room (nursery or study). Most inhabitants state that the internal doors are always open, so it was assumed that the upstairs was also hygrothermally coupled.

Blower-door-tests were also conducted in these 28 houses and six other houses.

2.2 Investigated flats in KW-project

An apartment building with 45 flats was built in 2009 as a social housing project. The GFA of the five-storey building is 5300 m² and the investigated flats have 55 - 110 m² net floor area. There are one storey flats and two storey maisonettes. Four of the investigated flats have bathrooms with a window; the other bathrooms have no window. A centralized balanced mechanical ventilation system is provided for all flats.

The external walls are made of reinforced concrete with ETICS on the exterior and plaster finish on the interior. The flat concrete roof has external thermal insulation. The external covering is either gravel or green roof. The interior partitions are either made of concrete or insulated stud walls with gypsum board.

Temperature and relative humidity loggers were placed in the living room and bedrooms of each investigated flat.

2.3 Questionnaires

Each participating household received a questionnaire regarding moisture production and ventilation behaviour.

The moisture production related questions were (a) How many persons live in the house/flat? (b) How many persons use the house/flat as a home office? (c) How often do you shower/bath per week? (d) Do you have a tumble dryer? (e) How often is the tumble dryer in use? (f) Where do you dry your clothes (if the tumble dryer is not in use)? (g) How many indoor plants do you have? (h) How often do you cook during one week? (i) Which pets do you have? (j) Do you use a humidifier/dehumidifier?

The ventilation related questions were (a) Do you have a mechanical ventilation system? (b) On which level does it operate? (c) How often do you open the windows per day? (d) How many windows are open the whole day/night? (e) Do you have an additional fan in the bathroom or the toilet? (f) At what levels do you use it?

2.4 Measurement equipment

The temperature and relative humidity was measured using T&D RTR 53 and HOBO U12 data logger. Loggers collected instantaneous values at 15 minutes (PSG) or hourly intervals (KW) for this study. The n_{50} -values were measured with a Minneapolis Blower DoorTM.

3. Questionnaire results

3.1 Questionnaire results in PSG

3.1.1 *Moisture production*

One to four persons live in the houses. All households use this house as their principal residence. Some of the families have small children and the house is occupied more often during the day. In other houses, the people work all day and the house is only occupied during the evening and night. Ten households have a tumble dryer. Most of the others hang the laundry in the living area (living room, bedroom, study, ...). Some of the houses do not have any indoor plants. One household has 39 plants. The families cook lunch or dinner between one and twelve times per week. The number of pets varies between zero and three. No household has an aquarium. The household that produces the most moisture due to pets is a family with two dogs. One family has a humidifier.

3.1.2 *Ventilation behaviour*

None of the houses have a mechanical ventilation system. Seven families open some windows in the morning for a short time. Fifteen families open windows for short periods in the morning and in the evening. Only six families open several windows more than twice a day. Two families have a window open for half a day. In four houses, there is one window open the whole night. All households use the fans in the bathroom and in the toilet. The fans switch on at a relative humidity between 50 % and 100 %.

3.2 Questionnaire results in KW

All moisture production-related answers are in the same range as in the PSG-project. Two families have a tumble dryer.

The largest difference to the PSG-project is the mechanical ventilation system in the KW project. One family uses the ventilation system on high; all others set it on low. The families open their windows less often than in the PSG-project. No additional fans are installed in the bathrooms and toilets as the mechanical system constantly extracts air from the bathrooms and toilets.

4. Measurement results

4.1 Measurement results in PSG

Monthly average temperatures vary between 19 and 24 °C on the ground floor and between 18 and 24 °C upstairs (FIG 1). The mean temperature of all measured houses in the basement (20.9 °C) is 0.5 K higher than the mean value of all measured upper floors (20.4 °C). The monthly mean relative humidity varies from 40 % to 70 %.

FIG 1. Histograms of measured monthly mean temperature (left) and monthly mean relative humidity (right) in January 2013 in the PSG-project.

The mean of all measured n_{50} -values is 0.68/h. The lowest n_{50} -value is 0.45/h, the second highest is 0.87/h. All houses are very airtight probably as the houses are prefabricated.

4.2 Measurement results in KW

Histograms of measured temperature and relative humidity can be seen in FIG 2.

FIG 2. Histograms of measured monthly mean temperature (left) and monthly mean relative humidity (right) in January 2013 in the KW-project.

4.3 External climate

The external temperature and relative humidity were measured at the PSG-project, at the KW-project and at our institute. All three positions are within 6 km distance of each other.

The monthly mean values in January 2013, measured by the two loggers in PSG, were 0.35 °C and 77 % relative humidity which results in an absolute humidity of 0.0039 kg/m³. At the KW-project 1.80 °C and 69 % were measured with two loggers similar to PSG. The weather station at our institute measured monthly mean values of 1.30 °C and 74 % relative humidity. Both result in the same absolute humidity of 0.0039 kg/m³.

5. Prediction of indoor humidity using questionnaire-results

For the prediction of indoor humidity from the questionnaires a formerly presented model was used (Harreither et al. 2012), improved and described in detail. The absolute humidity in the flats was calculated from the measured external temperature and literature values for moisture production and ventilation, applied to the data from the questionnaires. The internal volume of the flats was taken from the architectural plans. Internal moisture excess, Δv , is then calculated by using EN ISO 13788 (2012).

$$\Delta v = v_i - v_e = \frac{G}{n \cdot V} \quad (1)$$

Where

v_i	humidity of indoor air by volume (kg/m ³)
v_e	humidity of outdoor air by volume (kg/m ³)
G	internal moisture production rate (kg/h)
n	air change rate (1/h)
V	internal volume of building (m ³)

5.1 Moisture production

According to Kalamees et al. (2006), a person who is at home all the time produces 0.9 kg water vapour per day caused by respiration, transpiration, etc. Furthermore, it was assumed that a full-time employee is at home half a day (12 hours) and produces 0.45 kg/day. A part-time employee is at home 18 hours a day and produces 0.68 kg/day. Small children are assumed to be at home 18 hours a day and produce only 50 % the moisture an adult does (0.34 kg/day). Children in high school are assumed to be at home 14 hours a day and produce 75 % the moisture of an adult (0.39 kg/day). Someone who works from a “home-office” is considered to always be at home.

Literature values for moisture production due to personal hygiene are around 0.16 kg/shower, 0.33 kg/bathing and 0.08 kg/towel-drying (Kalamees et al. 2006, Hartmann et al. 2009, DIN Fachbericht 4108-8 2010). If the bathroom has a window or a fan, half of the value (for showering and bathing) is taken. If there are two windows, a quarter of the literature values is taken for the calculation. It is assumed that most of the moisture goes directly to the outside by windows or the fan and does not affect the measurement in the bedroom.

We identified out of the questionnaires that people in KW do their laundry approximately every fourth day. Assuming that one load evaporates 2.25 kg water (Hartmann et al. 2009), one person produces 0.55 kg water vapour per day by hanging laundry to dry. Some households are assumed to produce only 0.1 kg moisture per day due to drying the laundry with a tumble dryer or hanging the laundry outside the flat such as in a cellar or on a balcony.

For plants, moisture production of 0.05 kg/day/plant (Hartmann et al. 2009) was adopted. The mean number of plants per household is 6.6.

Cooking was assumed to produce 0.2 kg water vapour per event and per person (Kalamees et al. 2006, Hartmann et al. 2009).

15 households have pets. Dogs were assumed to produce 0.4 kg moisture/day; cats produce 0.1 kg/day. There were no other animals relevant for internal moisture production.

An additional production rate of 1.6 kg/day was calculated in one flat because of a humidifier. Nevertheless the absolute humidity is still low in this flat because of a tumble dryer, their inhabitants being at work all the time and open a window at night.

FIG 3 shows box plots of the moisture production rates per event and the overall internal moisture load per person.

FIG 3. Box plots of moisture production per household caused by different events and overall per person

5.2 Ventilation

The air change rates by a mechanical ventilation system, window opening and infiltration were summed to get the total air change rate (FIG 4).

FIG 4. Total air change rates in the flats/households due to different ventilation measures

The high air change rate due to the ventilation system was assumed to be 0.6/h and low 0.3/h.

The air change by window opening was calculated according to Reiß et al. (2009). An air change rate of 1/h for the whole flat was assumed for short airing periods by window opening in the morning or in the evening. For long periods of open windows during night or day (12 hours either during the day or night) an air change rate of 1/h is calculated for the room with the open window.

The fans in the bathroom are already taken into account when calculating the moisture production by showering or bathing.

The air change rate due to infiltration is calculated using Annex C in EN ISO 13789 (2007). The air change rate due to infiltration is 7 % of the n_{50} -value. In the KW-project, no n_{50} -values were measured. Therefore the mean n_{50} -value of the PSG-project was used to calculate the air change rate due to infiltration.

An additional air change rate of 0.05/h was assumed in one flat because of a dehumidifier.

5.3 Comparison of calculations and measurements

FIG 5 shows the calculated absolute humidity on the horizontal axis and the measured absolute humidity on the vertical axis.

FIG 5. Comparison of calculated and measured absolute humidity

The calculated results match the measured values if the humidity is low to average. When absolute indoor humidity is very high, the calculation shows variance from the measured values. The calculation with a maximum of 15 g/m³ exceeds the measured maximum of 11.9 g/m³. There seems to be a maximum moisture content, which is not exceeded.

The seven houses with the highest calculated indoor humidity were occupied during January 2013. In the measured data it can be seen that none of the families were on holiday. One theory for the deviation is condensation on the windows or other “condensate-catchers”. Some families told us during the survey that they sometimes wipe condensation from the windows in PSG. Moisture production rates as well as ventilation rates are not constant values, but vary (Johansson et al. 2011). The calculation could more accurately reproduce the measurements by using the upper boundary production value and the lower ventilation boundary value.

6. Conclusions and future work

An improved model for the prediction of indoor humidity was presented in this work. The correlation is very good for low to medium indoor humidity. Further research is needed for airtight residences with high indoor humidity.

The number of questionnaires returned was high in both projects. The period of time to complete the questionnaires seems to be acceptable due to the high return rate. Perhaps an even more accurate questionnaire can be used during the planning process for individual homeowners when designing their own homes.

Future work should be done to determine why an already high indoor humidity is still overestimated using this model. A more probability-based approach can also be implemented in the model if the literature provides distributions for moisture production and ventilation rates instead of single values.

7. Acknowledgements

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